

Knowledge Diffusion in the Global Innovation Index

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In the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII), knowledge diffusion refers to the process through which innovation and technological knowledge spread among individuals, companies, and countries. It is a crucial component of global competitiveness, as it determines how effectively an economy can distribute the benefits of innovation. Knowledge diffusion goes beyond the mere transmission of information and includes the ability to transfer skills, technologies, and business models. In the GII, knowledge diffusion is measured through indicators that assess a country's ability to export high-tech products, license technologies, and attract foreign direct investment (FDI) linked to technology. It also reflects a country's capacity to absorb technologies and ideas from external sources, promoting the transfer of knowledge through international collaboration, trade, and patents. In summary, knowledge diffusion is a key indicator for evaluating a country's openness and ability to integrate and utilize innovation, contributing to global economic progress and increased competitiveness. The data covers the period between 2013 and 2022.

Global Knowledge Diffusion in 2022. The 2022 Global Innovation Index data on knowledge diffusion shows significant variation between countries, reflecting their openness to innovation, ability to transfer technologies and skills, and degree of connection with the global economy. Ireland leads the ranking with a score of 73.3, due to a technology-export-oriented economy and the presence of numerous innovative multinationals. Finland and Israel follow with scores above 67, highlighting dynamic innovation ecosystems well integrated internationally. Japan, Switzerland, and Sweden show solid results, reflecting strong investments in research and development, as well as the ability to spread technological knowledge through patents and collaborations. Among emerging economies, India (50.8) and China (48.2) stand out for their enormous growth potential and increasing capacity to absorb and disseminate innovations. However, Italy ranks relatively low with a score of 41, indicating some difficulties in adopting and spreading technological knowledge compared to major advanced countries. Countries at the bottom of the ranking, such as Nigeria (2.3) and Iraq (0.8), reflect challenges related to weak infrastructure, political instability, and low integration into global innovation flows, limiting the diffusion of knowledge.

Global Knowledge Diffusion from 2013 to 2022. Data on knowledge diffusion from 2013 to 2022 reveals significant variations, with some nations making great strides forward while others experienced heavy setbacks. This dynamic reflects countries' and economies' ability to leverage the diffusion of technological knowledge to innovate and thrive economically, as well as failures to do so. Some countries have seen spectacular improvements in terms of knowledge diffusion. For instance, the United Arab Emirates witnessed an impressive increase from 0.4 to 36.4, a 9000% growth. This reflects the country's massive investment in innovation, advanced technologies, and economic diversification. Similarly, Qatar registered extraordinary growth (1126%), rising from 1.5 to 18.4, a clear sign of its post-oil development strategy. Panama followed a similar trajectory (+429.41%), leveraging its geographical position and growing role as a hub for trade and logistics. Other countries benefiting from significant improvements include Cyprus (+117.92%) and Estonia

(+126.23%), which consolidated their positions as leaders in innovation and technology within the European Union. The Philippines (+65.06%) made great progress thanks to its expanding tech sector and growing startup ecosystem. Many advanced economies like Japan (+29.88%), Germany (+25.62%), and South Korea (+21.37%) continued to improve, but at a more moderate pace. This could indicate that, being already well-positioned, they face challenges in maintaining continuous growth in knowledge diffusion. However, these countries remain global leaders in technological innovation and knowledge transfer. Countries like India (+21.24%) and Vietnam (+15.67%) also showed significant improvements, but their growth rates were more contained compared to other emerging economies, signaling a growing integration into global knowledge flows. On the opposite front, a significant number of countries saw a substantial decline in knowledge diffusion. Hong Kong experienced a dramatic decline (-85.48%), as did Nigeria (-86.78%) and Angola (-91.10%). The drastic fall in Hong Kong can be attributed to recent political turmoil and a shift in its global economic role. Countries like Tajikistan (-87.25%) and Benin (-93.75%) saw steep regressions, suggesting structural problems in adapting to global technologies and knowledge diffusion. The negative performance of Kuwait (-55.56%) is concerning for an energy-based economy, highlighting its difficulty in diversifying towards more innovative sectors. Countries like Mali (-54.60%) and Senegal (-56.92%) saw significant reductions, likely due to weaknesses in innovation infrastructure and a lack of investment in high-tech sectors. The data highlights that knowledge diffusion is heavily influenced by investments in innovation, political stability, and the ability to integrate into global economic flows. While some emerging and advanced economies have made significant progress, many others struggle to keep pace, often due to internal challenges such as political instability, weak infrastructure, or lack of economic diversification. These trends clearly show that technological progress and knowledge diffusion are essential for long-term economic growth.

Conclusions. On average, the level of knowledge diffusion declined for the countries considered between 2013 and 2022, dropping from 27.8 units to 27.1 units, with an average decrease of 2.48%. The top performers, meaning countries where knowledge diffusion grew significantly, are: the United Arab Emirates with +9000%, Qatar with +1126.67%, Panama with +429.41%, Iran with +237.93%, and Ethiopia with +136.84%. The worst performers are Tajikistan with -87.25%, Angola with -91.10%, Brunei Darussalam with -92.65%, Benin with -93.75%, and Guinea with -93.87%.

	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	United Arab Emirates	0,4	36,4	36	9000,00
	Qatar	1,5	18,4	16,9	1126,67
	Panama	5,1	27	21,9	429,41
	Iran, Islamic Rep.	2,9	9,8	6,9	237,93
	Ethiopia	3,8	9	5,2	136,84
Worse Performers	Tajikistan	54,1	6,9	-47,2	-87,25
	Angola	38,2	3,4	-34,8	-91,10
	Brunei Darussalam	27,2	2	-25,2	-92,65
	Benin	24	1,5	-22,5	-93,75
	Guinea	50,6	3,1	-47,5	-93,87

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Country	2022	Country	2022	Country	2022
Ireland	73,3	Lithuania	34,1	Honduras	14,9
Finland	70	Kuwait	33,6	Albania	14,6
Israel	67,3	New Zealand	33,4	Cambodia	14,3
Netherlands	65,4	Sri Lanka	32,9	Paraguay	14
Japan	65,2	Portugal	30,9	Namibia	13,3
Switzerland	63,4	Norway	30,2	Madagascar	12,1
Sweden	63,4	Bosnia and Herzegovina	28,9	Nicaragua	12,1
Singapore	59,1	Uruguay	27,7	Ghana	12
United States	57,9	North Macedonia	27	Montenegro	11,7
Germany	55,9	Panama	27	Niger	11,5
Korea, Rep.	55,1	Tunisia	26,1	Myanmar	11,4

United Kingdom	54,5	Bahrain	25,6	Senegal	10,9
Cyprus	52,3	Armenia	25,4	Cote d'Ivoire	10,7
Philippines	51,5	Moldova	25,4	Uzbekistan	10,7
India	50,8	Saudi Arabia	25,3	Iran, Islamic Rep.	9,8
Czechia	50,6	El Salvador	24,8	Yemen, Rep.	9,1
Hungary	50,5	Greece	24,3	Ethiopia	9
France	50,4	Luxembourg	24,3	Peru	8,9
China	48,2	Guatemala	23,9	Nepal	8,7
Denmark	47,9	Brazil	23,7	Uganda	8,5
Austria	46,8	Russian Federation	23,6	Bangladesh	8,2
Malaysia	46	Kenya	23,2	Togo	8,2
Belgium	45,4	Turkiye	22,8	Botswana	7,9
Romania	44,8	Morocco	22,6	Burkina Faso	7,7
Iceland	44,1	Argentina	22,3	Zambia	7,5
Estonia	41,4	Indonesia	22,3	Zimbabwe	7
Italy	41	Kazakhstan	20,8	Tajikistan	6,9
Malta	39,8	Australia	20,3	Tanzania	6,4
Costa Rica	39,1	Colombia	20,1	Cameroon	6,1
Canada	38,8	South Africa	20,1	Ecuador	6
Belarus	38,5	Trinidad and Tobago	19,6	Mongolia	5,9
Latvia	38,5	Dominican Republic	18,9	Azerbaijan	5,4
Slovenia	38,2	Pakistan	18,7	Rwanda	5,2
Slovak Republic	37,6	Qatar	18,4	Algeria	4,8
Poland	37,4	Chile	17,6	Mozambique	3,8
				Hong Kong SAR,	
Thailand	37,4	Lao PDR	17,5	China	3,5
Bulgaria	37,1	Mauritius	17,3	Angola	3,4
Spain	37,1	Georgia	17,2	Mauritania	3,3
Mexico	36,7	Oman	16,9	Guinea	3,1
United Arab Emirates	36,4	Jordan	16,3	Nigeria	2,3
Serbia	35,8	Egypt, Arab Rep.	16	Brunei Darussalam	2
Ukraine	35,4	Jamaica	16	Burundi	1,8
Croatia	35,3	Mali	15,8	Benin	1,5
Vietnam	34,7	Kyrgyz Republic	15,1	Iraq	0,8

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